

The Patterns of Corruption in Institutions of Higher Learning in Zimbabwe: A General Overview from State Universities 2000–2008

Zimbabwe, at the turn of the new millennium, has seen an increase in the number of institutions of higher learning driven by the growing number of people demanding higher education. The government is trying to create these new institutions to meet the development goals of a Southern country. The creation and overall development of these institutions is accompanied by growing corruption. This paper seeks to analyse the dimensions of corruption that have emerged and to evaluate the specific types of corruption that have affected the overall nurturing of the human resource base necessary for the development of Zimbabwe.

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Introduction

To begin with, it is important to highlight, as the Zimbabwean case shows, that corruption, among other factors, has had serious negative impacts on service delivery and overall achievement of set objectives and expected outcomes. One of the ways in which corruption affects development is a distortion of resource allocation. Institutions of higher learning, whose numbers have increased to cater to a growing demand in higher education, were historically thought to be immune from corrupt practices by virtue of their centrality in the training of leaders in commerce, politics and society at large. But recently it has been seen that corruption has impacted education as in all other sectors. This has been happening in the context of an increased demand for education following independence in Africa.

In the light of the economic and political environment prevalent in Zimbabwe in the twenty-first century, these newly created institutions had to grapple with a number of challenges, which in turn, have led to the emergence and exacerbation of corrupt practices. This has resulted in an increasing loss of confidence and the rise in cultural practices that affect the educational institutions, which are places for imparting knowledge and making people more disciplined. This paper seeks to provide a general overview of the occurrence of corrupt practices in Zimbabwe's state-owned universities. The paper begins with a study of the background to corruption in institutions of higher learning, providing a conceptual and comparative framework of analysis with other institutions globally, particularly those in the Southern countries. It will then provide in detail the patterns of corruption in the state universities paying particular attention to causes, forms and impact. Further, the paper examines and evaluates the solutions that have been put in place to combat corruption. Policies that need to be taken into consideration to win a war against such malpractices will also be proffered.

Historical Background to Corruption and its Prevalence in Institutions of Higher Learning

Philip G. Altbach in defining corruption noted that a dictionary definition which captures it as an 'impairment of integrity, virtue, or moral principle... inducement to wrong by improper or unlawful means', well captures the meaning when it comes to academia and institutions of higher learning.¹ However, it is important to state at the very beginning that one needs to separate some acts of mere incompetence and inadequacies by some actors and those that fall under corrupt practices.²

According to Miynt U, corruption is defined

as the use of public office for private gain, or in other words, use of official position, rank or status by an office bearer for his own personal benefit. Following from this definition, examples of corrupt behaviour would include: (a) Bribery, (b) extortion, (c) fraud, (d) embezzlement, (e) nepotism, (f) cronyism, (g) appropriation of public assets and property for private use, and (h) influence peddling.³

Corruption denotes the abuse of power or authority vested in an office for personal gain. In essence it is subversion of public interest by personal interest or simply put, anything that negatively affects clean administration of the institutions of higher learning. The overall effect is that the best qualified people for the job cease to count because loyalty rather than ability to do the job directs appointments. When it comes to the admission and grading of students the best qualified are denied places and good grades, which go to the less deserving who are related or somehow connected to office-bearers and those who determine grading.

To exemplify, in a corrupt institution or state 'productive resources are deployed in such a way that they favour those in power, their relatives and yes men or women.'⁴ It is also important to highlight that corruption is largely a hidden transaction which the involved parties like to keep secret and that the 'most widely condemned practices (e.g. kickbacks on government contracts) are also the most hidden, while more visible practices (e.g. forced private tutoring) tend to be more tolerated.'⁵

El Hadji I. Sall differentiates between what is

termed 'according to rule' corruption and 'against the rule.' Facilitation payments, where a bribe is paid

to receive preferential treatment for something that the bribe receiver is required to do by law, constitute the former. The latter, on the other hand, is a bribe paid to obtain services from the bribe receiver is prohibited from providing.⁶

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The key to understanding corruption is the discretionary powers the office-holder has in relation to certain benefits and services he can dispense. Crucially, it is difficult to have control on these powers since excessive checks will lead to failure of services. According to Miynt, this is also related to the concept of economic rent, which says 'a person who owns... a special asset can charge more than normal price for its use and earn economic rent or monopoly profit.'⁷

The concept of economic rent and how it is directly linked to corruption has aptly been captured by Klitgaard's equation (as cited by Miynt): $C=R+D-A$, where C stands for Corruption, R for economic rent, D for discretionary powers, and A for accountability. Miynt explains this to mean, ... [T]he more opportunities for economic rent (R) exist in a country, the larger will be the corruption. Similarly, the greater the discretionary powers (D) granted to administrators, the greater will be the corruption. However, the more administrators are held accountable (A) for their actions, the less will be the corruption, and hence a minus sign in front of A .⁸

Miynt says corrupt tendencies are likely to emerge if

Administrators are granted large discretionary powers with respect to interpreting rules, they are given a lot of freedom to decide on how rules are to be applied, to whom and in what manner they are to be applied, are vested with powers to amend, alter, and rescind the rules, and even to supplement the rules by invoking new restrictive administrative measures and procedures; and there are no effective mechanisms and institutional arrangements in the country to hold administrators accountable for their action.⁹

This has been the case when new institutions are being set up as is the case in Zimbabwe's state universities in the twenty-first century.

The occurrence of corruption in institutions of higher learning has a wider scope than once thought in conventional wisdom. It occurs or originates at almost all levels of the higher education sector, i.e. at the political, administrative, and classroom level. The taxonomy of corruption in the education system in general thus begins at the political level through procurement and accreditation. Here the buyer is the educational institution and the seller is the government, usually the ministry of education. At the administrative level it involves obtaining illegal entrance to specialised programmes, having grades raised through illegal payments, including those for normal educational services (housing, library use, computer access, information access, administrative procedures, etc.). The buyer is the student and the seller is either a member of the faculty or the administration. At the classroom level, obtaining requisite information, assistance in students' work, accessing relevant and lucrative attachments, etc., the student becomes the buyer and the seller a member of the department.

In Zimbabwe, corruption has become entrenched in institutions of higher learning as a result of substantial changes in the political and economic system that have taken place at the turn of the century. This has been coupled with increased number of state universities accompanied by increased enrolments.

Corruption in state universities (apart from those that take place at the political level) occurs at specific times in the educational calendar. Those that involve students usually occur at the beginning of the semester during admissions and in the run-up to and during the examination period and when grants are allocated.

The Patterns of Corruption in State Universities

Causes of corruption

Conventionally, selfishness and greed are thought to be the two most powerful forces stoking corruption the world over. Some individuals practice corruption, not only to get richer than their colleagues but also to be admired for their skills in outwitting authorities. Because of selfishness, corrupt people turn a blind eye to the suffering that their corruption inflicts on others, and they justify bribery simply because they benefit from it. The more material benefits they amass, the greedier they become.

However, as the Zimbabwean case demonstrates, it is important to note that there are other factors emanating from the environment that need a close review and analysis. For institutions of higher learning in contemporary Zimbabwe, there is a clear correlation between economic factors and corruption.¹⁰ Various stakeholders in institutions of higher learning are short of money and this puts great pressure to alter systems and regulations for the purposes of obtaining benefits. Faculty members and administrators may be looking for ways to supplement woefully inadequate salaries in a society lacking other opportunities for employment. For example, a lecturer earns 2 trillion Zimbabwean dollars and this is only enough to buy a loaf of bread.¹¹ Further, the economic environment existing in Zimbabwe in the 21st century has seen most workers in state universities living below the poverty datum line, which as of 2008 was at USD 150 when the average lecturer salary was USD 5. This coupled with external pressures to admit and promote students with monetary and other benefits increases corrupt tendencies.

At the same time, employees feel resentment over bad management or pay levels that they think to be unfair. This makes them feel justified in making false expense claims or taking bribes. People with pitifully low wages come to feel that they have no option but to demand bribes in order to make a decent living. And when those who extort bribes or pay them to gain an unfair advantage go unpunished, few are prepared to swim against the tide.¹²

Politicians seek money to use for patronage, which they argue to be essential to prevent political instability and unrest. Faculty and administrators with woefully low salaries serve the moneyed classes who are prepared to go to any length to get their wishes fulfilled. Officials need extra money to maintain their standards of living if salaries have not been raised to match inflation, to meet commitments for housing, car, school fees, etc.

Politicians and officials who fear loss of office seek corrupt benefits as a cover, especially if they can expect no pension. University officials resort to corruption for a secure retired life. At the same time, once one becomes corrupt, one will try by all means possible to ensnare as many colleagues as possible within his or her rackets. This might be caused by weak leadership qualities which lead to hiring people closely linked to oneself to curtail the emergence of dissenting voices when things go wrong

The other cause is cultural. According to Altbach, (T)raditions of higher education also play a role. Universities everywhere have European roots and organizational patterns— they may not be well suited to some non-Western societies. This historical disjunction may make it easier for corruption to take hold. Further, in many developing countries, universities were part of a colonial system, and the values of subservience were to some extent put into place by the colonial powers. Countries without deep academic traditions may also have looser ties to the traditional values of academe.¹³

Some societies have evolved systems without well-developed meritocratic norms and hence are often prone to academic corruption. The idea that someone can be promoted or can receive an academic degree because he or she is from a particular group or has certain familial links is seen as acceptable. Moreover universities have personnel from different institutions across the world where norms that are regarded as corrupt are often also not questioned.

Another cause that is central in Zimbabwe's state universities is that the institutions are politicised. Thus, nonacademic norms of many kinds impinge on universities paving the way for corrupt tendencies. Where affiliation to political parties is the basis of appointment to certain offices,

it has a great bearing on the functioning of the institutions as political consideration rather than professionalism takes precedence. In practical terms it means, therefore, that political parties become active on campus, dominating 'academic governance bodies and [putting] their followers in positions of influence.'¹⁴ In essence, where politics is injected into academic institutions, forces determining decisions become located elsewhere other than in the university itself.

The direct result of party politics infiltrating into university administration is the emergence of a weak leadership among student and staff. A weak leadership is responsible for permitting corruption to entrench itself in the university. As corruption entrenches itself in the organisation the chances of a strong leadership becomes more improbable.

Students and other stakeholders also want to satisfy their needs and wants without working for them. For students, obtaining a qualification with better grades with minimum effort is worth the hassles and risks accompanying corrupt practices. Maintaining and enhancing corruption becomes the *sine qua non* of the existence of other beneficiaries, particularly cronies of the corrupt officers.

Dimensions of corruption

As it pertains to students, corrupt practices emerge from the admission process itself. Admission is for sale in some institutions. Well-connected applicants or those who bribe or otherwise influence the academic authorities responsible for admissions gain entry regardless of their academic qualifications. In such situations, graduation is a virtual certainty, whether or not a student completes the required academic work— a process sometimes smoothed by further bribery or influence-peddling.¹⁵ When appointments are made on the basis of who one knows, one becomes loyal to the appointer not the public that is supposed to be served. Cases of improper rearrangement of admission lists and illegal changes in the quotas of students who pay and those who do not pay full fees abound across the country.

The next stage where corrupt tendencies are visible in most institutions is that of examinations. The variety of means used to cheat at examinations is long and, in a perverse way, is indicative of the inventiveness of a corrupt system. In some places, professors or administrators collude with students by selling examination papers in advance or by 'fixing' the results. In countries where oral examinations are common, there are further possibilities for corruption. Professors will at times openly solicit bribes for grades of an exam. For example, some faculty members will exchange sexual favours for passes right from the continuous assessment (coursework) stage up to and including the examinations proper. Thus, teachers are openly abusing their right to examine in order to ease or benefit certain students or in some cases, are making their examinations more difficult in order to get a bribe.

In other cases, students manage to steal question papers and sell them in advance to others. Websites are now selling research papers to undergraduate students, who then sometimes submit the papers as their own. A quick survey indicated that a significant proportion of students admit to cheating at examinations from time to time. Students also have the tendency of paying another student to take an exam on their behalf.

In some situations lecturers also have the tendency of forcing students to buy their texts or modules in order to pass an exam. They also make such texts and modules prerequisites for all students taking their courses. Where oral examinations are involved such as those in foreign languages and dissertation defences, such arrangements have occasionally been unfairly manipulated to the disadvantage of targeted students consequently benefitting those favoured by lecturers.

Thirdly, records are manipulated for the benefit of some students. For example, when tabulating marks at the end of a semester some grades are changed to improve the overall grades of students. At the same time, some authorities will also try to influence situations such that the records of the failures of their relatives and cronies can be removed from the system. This is rampant in situations where institutions use outdated data management systems that are deliberately left in place for easy manipulation.

The fourth area is that of the library and access to computers since in most institutions, such

resources are at a premium. In this regard, some students are allocated rare texts for use over long periods of time while others never get the chance to use such texts. Such 'unconnected' students also rarely get the chance to use computers, which are usually far outnumbered by the student population—a situation where each student should get the minimum possible time if they are all to get the chance to use these resources.

There is a fifth dimension of corruption pertaining to students. Regulations pertaining to registration procedures and timing are often relaxed. As a result inflation erodes the value of fees the students are to pay, since they tend to pay at the end of the semester rather than at the beginning. Examination regulations are also left unenforced or changed from time to time as and when it suits the powers that be.

On the part of the staff, corrupt practices start from the point of employment. Academic posts are often 'sold' in the sense that those seeking appointments to lectureships or professorships must curry favour with selection committees through gifts or other emoluments. In some cases, academic posts are also awarded on the basis of ethnic and geographic backgrounds. Emergence of categories, like Wasu (from Manicaland), and Wezhira (from Masvingo), have led to recruitment and promotion along geographical lines. In such cases, an individual in a position of influence will ensure that his kith and kin get positions as and when vacancies arise.

Second, in matters of promotion, there is a tendency for information regarding the operation of the committees remaining the preserve of a chosen few. Some who are not privileged will never get to know the stipulated dates when it is time to apply for promotion. In universities with a rigid academic hierarchy, senior academics often promote their friends or perhaps colleagues without regard to the qualifications of the candidates. Furthermore, a pervasive gender bias exists (e.g. the bypassing of objective student assessment criteria). This also constitutes an abuse of power, and, therefore, an act of corruption. A promotion and/or recruitment purely on the basis of gender is a form of corruption that entrenches the interests of men.¹⁶

Third, in the case of staff benefits, only a few privileged and well-connected members with prior knowledge of the availability of scarce commodities manage to benefit from these. When the rest of the staff members get to hear of the availability of these they would have long since run out. For example, in an environment of scarcity, such commodities like fuel, cement, foodstuffs would under normal circumstances be equally distributed amongst all staff members, but this does not happen in the majority of cases as only a chosen few get to enjoy these.

Fourthly, resources necessary for research which should also be enjoyed equally by all teaching staff end up being reserved for a connected few. Funding to carry out research and attend conferences and workshops, which should be the lifeblood of any academic, is abused for the benefit of a few. This also has adverse effects on publications as the 'economy of affection'¹⁷ will affect peer review mechanisms often allowing plagiarism and publication of weak papers. Although plagiarism can be found in almost every academic system, in some it is widespread and tacitly accepted, at least no one asks too many questions, and the penalties for detection are few. In some instances, corruption in this field may produce results or even entire research projects. Lecturers and professors also tend to take students' work and publish it as their own.

Fifthly, the division within a university which is responsible for the allocation of office space, and residential accommodation is also wide open to corrupt tendencies. Such a division will be inundated by staff members requiring that they get residential services and office space. Office-bearers who have the power to make such allocations often extort bribes.

In the prevailing economic environment, many universities are now trying to generate income by designating various modes of entry with differential fee structures. This has given opportunities to lecturers to practice another form of corruption. Instead of teaching different categories of students separately, for which they also get paid separately, they resort to teaching them together. This, however, is in response to late payments made by corrupt administrators in order to benefit from the highly inflationary situation. Lecturers also offer illegal coaching sessions to students who can pay for them.

There is a high degree of general misappropriation of resources such as bond paper, printing facilities, and photocopying services. Staff members are in the habit of using institutional resources such as computers, printers, photocopiers and bond paper to do tasks that benefit them individually such as typing, printing and photocopying of student assignments, dissertations and books for payment.

When purchasing commodities, supplies and assets, normal tender and procurement procedures are either circumvented or tenders are awarded to those who are prepared to pay bribes to get the contracts or tenders. Where tenders are not necessary, lower-level staff are in the habit of inflating quotations and awarding the orders to their cronies. Academic staff also habitually make claims for tasks that they do not do, such as out of campus activities like supervision of students on attachment. When accounts are settled, sums paid back are rendered so miniscule by inflation that they do not affect the staff members concerned. Many institutions also lose large sums through the payment of salaries and other benefits to ghost workers. The high rate of staff turnover at state universities has led to this practice becoming widespread.

Departments of students' affairs is also one open to abuse and corrupt practices, for instance in the allocation of on-campus accommodation. Officials often take bribes for such allocation. The same is true of the security wing of universities, which are willing to turn a blind eye to students' misdemeanours such as squatting, cooking, drinking alcohol on campus and other offences.

Impacts of corruption

In general, it has been recognised that corruption hurts the poor disproportionately by diverting funds intended for development, undermining a government's ability to provide basic services, feeding inequality and injustice and discouraging foreign investment and aid. In Zimbabwe's state universities, corruption has fueled a general decline in standards, high rate of staff turnover, increase in the rates of academic failure, and inability to attract donors and private sector players.

Nepotism in recruitment leads to a lack of quality among academic and non-academic staff, jeopardising not just the development of the institutions but the country in general. This impact may be difficult to assess at this point in time, but its repercussions will become apparent in the long-run.

Corruption has become so widespread that it is spiralling out of control, severely impacting governance.¹⁸ Those who have tried to rein it in have often been victimised by colleagues and superiors. Whistleblowers risk losing benefits and opportunities. Further, students nurtured in such a corrupt system will only end up promoting it throughout their own careers, contributing to the development of an underground political economy.

We have already said that in a corrupt system, the privileged and the well-connected enjoy economic rent. The concentration of wealth in the hands of a few, distorts consumption patterns to feed the lifestyle of the new and extremely rich university elite. In Zimbabwe, this involves imports of a large variety of luxury goods like expensive consumer goods. Corruption also enables mid-level managers in present day Zimbabwe, whose salaries are just adequate to buy a loaf of bread, to afford a decent living.

The battle against corruption is difficult to wage as long as salaries remain so low that survival demands resort to illegitimate practices. The issue of complicity compounds the problem further. When corruption infiltrates the highest levels of education institutions and the state itself, it becomes difficult to fight as those in charge of oversight are themselves implicated. Underlings thrive, knowing that they have the protection of the bosses. Even in the few cases that the culprits are actually caught and punished, they are invariably the small fry. Given the highly political nature of appointments of the top university bras and their seeming invulnerability, the crusade against corruption has to begin at the highest echelons. This requires political will at the national level. Unfortunately, national leaders are not concerned with the petty corruption that plagues universities.

Challenges in ending corruption

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In this context, an interesting initiative is being undertaken in Zimbabwe through a programme called Tip-Off Anonymous. It enables members of the public to act as whistle-blowers while protecting their anonymity. For such initiatives to work, what is required a multi-sectoral approach and the involvement of all interested parties.

The Future of Corruption in Institutions of Higher learning

There are many mechanisms that a country or a university needs to adopt to lessen the possibility of corruption and to lower the perception that it is corrupt. These include codes of conduct for faculty, administrators and students; statements of honesty on websites available to the public; university 'courts' to hear cases of misconduct; and annual reports to the public on changes in the number and types of incidents.¹⁹ However commitment to end corruption has been hampered by the people concerned themselves. Alina made it clear that recognising corruption and being able to do something about it are two very different things.²⁰ In essence, therefore, the eradication of corruption requires that in addition to abhorring it there should be a clear will to weeding it out. Thus, if institutions of higher learning are to eradicate corruption, there is an urgent need to adopt a 'principled pragmatic' approach with strategic interventions that do not impose overly idealised standards.

The first step is effective policy intervention so as to acquire information about the experience and cost of corruption. One recommendation is that regular surveys be conducted, aimed at exposing areas where corruption is rampant and that their findings be published. Evidence from one such study indicated that with surveys being conducted at two points in time, the decline in corruption was significant, suggesting that when the possibility of exposure and professional embarrassment is real, the propensity to engage in corruption declines. Institutions of higher learning need to engage in intensive awareness-raising on modes and types of corruption as a prelude to tackling it. As the Internet has become a major tool of research and information-dissemination, Zimbabwean universities have to explore it if corruption is to be curbed.

State universities should continuously ensure that the underlying importance of quality, equity, efficiency and transparency in higher education is constantly emphasised and promoted. In this regard, they should strive to motivate and build capacity among students, including their representatives, to create a more transparent university environment.

In addition, all stakeholders, including the media, decision-makers and government should be involved in addressing the problem. Unfortunately, there is a lack of NGOs dealing directly with issues of higher education. In other words, the fight against corruption requires an alliance between the state, the civil society, the students, and the staff associations.

Capacity-building and institution-building through increased financial support is central to the task of ending corruption. Funds will also go a long way to improve effective teaching and research. Also, academic institutions require autonomy to build and support academic culture and values.

Institutions of higher learning need to establish independent and controllable quality assurance and accreditation systems with a mandate of setting up clear tools for assessing quality. This can in the long run plug a number of loopholes manipulated in the pursuit of corrupt practices.

Another area requiring immediate attention is the management of traditional exams, which needs urgent improvements if not a total overhaul. The academic community itself must understand that without integrity and meritocracy there can be no true university.

The international community should not be left out in the fight against corruption in the developing world. Developed countries specially have a huge responsibility to help poor institutions to develop with at least the minimum resources required.

Generally, there must be recognition that every corrupt transaction has two parties to it. We all have a responsibility to try to crack down on both ends of these transactions and contribute towards exposing malpractices that hamper development of the higher education sector not only in Zimbabwe but Africa as a whole. Ignoring the menace will have a negative repercussion for Africa's development.

To find holistic solutions, all institutions (local, national, regional and international) must engage with local political processes and societal structures to end corruption rather than relying on narrow technical solutions. It is apparent that poor governance has failed to curb corrupt practices.

The education sector is the largest or second largest budget item in most countries, and opportunities for corrupt practices are numerous. It is difficult to measure the prevalence of corruption but it is fair to estimate that it is widespread in South and South East Asia, and endemic in many countries in the Balkans, the former Soviet Union and Africa.

Where corruption is rampant there is a great risk that social trust may wither away and that the development potential of whole countries may be undermined. Adolescents often become familiar with corruption at schools and universities. When this happens, a central role of the education sector- namely the imparting of ethical values and behaviour- becomes impossible, resulting in corruption becoming the norm at all levels of society.

<http://www.u4.no/themes/education/educationmainpoints.cfm>, accessed on 20.02.2010.

Conclusion

It is important to note that a number of factors have contributed towards the emergence and the exacerbation of corrupt practices in Zimbabwe's state universities, particularly in the 21st century. These practices are found in almost all units of a university, and involve key stakeholders in the system itself. As we have highlighted, the negative effects that have resulted are enormous and if no energies and resources are employed to curb its spread, higher education institutions in Zimbabwe will face total collapse. We would like to move away from conventional recommendations that always leave the solution of the problem to the police, legal institutions and the key actors in these malpractices. For Zimbabwe, any solution should focus on a holistic approach that calls for the participation not only of the local but also the external actors, including international donors. The researchers contend that as long as resources remain scarce and continuously dwindle, corruption in state universities is not going to disappear in the immediate future and the risk of corruption becoming institutionalised will gain momentum. In essence, the reality of corruption in state universities in Zimbabwe must be exposed as a central problem, paving the way for its comprehension and its total elimination.

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11 This figure is in terms of the currency of Zimbabwe as it was before its revaluations between 2006 and 2009. The effect of the revaluation, however, was temporary, as spiraling inflation took hold almost immediately thereafter, restoring the general conditions described in this article, if not the specific details.

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